

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE DETECTOR FOR
COMPOSITE LAMINATED STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT - A low velocity impact surface damage detector for laminated composites and honeycomb sandwich structures has been developed. The basic principle used by the detector is Shadow Moire interferometry. When a structure is examined through a 4-inch x 5-inch viewing field of the detector, surface perturbations become visible in the form of Moire fringe patterns. The operation of the device is very simple and its detecting capability is not affected by temperature, humidity or vibration. It can be used in the operational field by personnel who have received minimal training to detect minute surface perturbations resulting from foreign object impact in composite laminate structures. The entire detector system weighing less than 3.5 lbs, is capable of detecting surface perturbations of less than 0.001 of an inch.

INTRODUCTION - Fatigue failure modes of composite structures differ considerably from those of metal structures. With metals, fatigue cracks generally initiate in the plane normal to the outer surface. With composites, however, damage often initiates internally because of impact or otherwise and propagates parallel to the laminate plane. Delamination is the major cause for failure of composite structures. Low velocity impact damage, which can lead to ultimate failure, usually is not readily observable by visual inspection.

The increased use of laminated composites and honeycomb sandwich structures on aircraft has necessitated the development of inspection techniques to detect the presence of disbonds, delaminations and other defects. These inspections help assure that composite structures provide the same level of structural reliability as comparable metal structures. A variety of non-destructive methods are currently available to detect internal damage in laminates. Ultrasonics and X-ray are commonly used in industrial applications. Thermographic, laser holography, acoustic emission, and simple hammer tapping have demonstrated varying degrees of success. But, none of them has exhibited the simplicity, reliability, flexibility and speed of the Shadow Moire out-of-plane Interferometric Damage Detector developed and described herein.

SHADOW MOIRE INTERFEROMETRY - Shadow Moire Interferometry is an extension of Moire Interferometry which deals with the interference fringes generated by the superposition of two sets of finely ruled parallel lines. One set is on a specimen which is commonly referred to as the specimen grid and the other set is on a reference plate which is referred to as the reference grid. In Shadow Moire, the specimen grid is replaced by the shadow of the reference grid. Since the light illuminates the specimen at an angle θ , as shown in Figure 1, the shadow grid projected on the surface of the specimen is distorted by the out-of-plane perturbation of the specimen surface. When viewed through the reference grid, the superposition of the two grids produces fringes which are clearly visible. These fringes can be used to detect the presence of minute local out-of-plane surface perturbations.

DESCRIPTION OF SHADOW MOIRE OUT-OF-PLANE INTERFEROMETRIC (SMOOPI) DAMAGE

DETECTOR - The SMOOPI Damage Detector shown in Figure 2, consists of an anodized aluminum frame on an extended pistol grip with attachments for easy installation of a 4-inch x 5-inch Moire grid. A 35 watt quartz light source with a .050-inch slit provides a collimating line light source, simulating a remote point source, is attached to the frame with a 6-inch support for simple adjustments of illuminator angle and verticle position. The light source is powered by a portable, shoulder-strap-mounted, rechargeable battery-pack or from an AC adapter. The entire detector system, including the battery-pack, weighs less than 3.5 lbs.

Grids with line densities up to 500 lpi were successfully used with the SMOOPI device. The best results were obtained, however, with a grid line density of 150 lpi. For cases with high local perturbation or poor contrast, lower line density grid of 50 lpi should be used; and in cases with a low perturbation field, a higher line density grid of 250 lpi or higher should be used.

MEASUREMENT AND DETECTION - When the Detector frame is placed in contact with the surface which has no surface local damage or perturbation, no fringe pattern appears. If the surface has a slight perturbation from flat, such as a local indentation or a lump, a series of equidistant parallel fringes are observed. In areas displaying one or more closed fringes (where each fringe represents a contour of a constant elevation), the general shape of the fringe pattern reveals the local surface topography of the perturbation. For example, spherical shaped indentations will give a fringe pattern of concentric circles.

The sensitivity of the detector depends on the illumination angle, grid density as well as the depth of the perturbation on the observed surface. The level difference Z, from one fringe to the next fringe can be calculated by the following equation:

$$Z = 1/(P \times \tan \theta)$$

Where P is the grid density in lines per inch (lpi) and θ is the angle of incidence between the light source and the normal of the specimen surface.

APPLICATIONS - The SmooPI Detector has been used successfully in the field to detect low velocity impact damage on monolithic composite laminated structures and composite and aluminum face sheet honeycomb core sandwich structures. It has also been successful in detecting progressive fatigue damage (delamination) around a hole in a 25 ply Gr/Ep laminate, Figure 3. The detector has no difficulty in identifying out-of-plane perturbations of less than 0.001 inch. In a different application, the device was used to assess the extent of the cold work experienced by holes in a metal plate after the hole was expanded, cold-worked, Figure 4, with a split sleeve.

CONCLUSIONS - The SMOOPI Damage Detector, a simple and low cost device, has proved to be a practical, effective, versatile and reliable in detecting impact damage in composite laminate and honeycomb sandwich structures. Delaminations and disbonds have also been successfully detected with a surface perturbation detection capability of .001 inch or less. Damage sites can be scanned and identified quickly. In the event further damage characterization becomes necessary, the flaw sites can be further analyzed and quantified with other NDE techniques.

Figure 1. Shadow Moiré: Schematic Diagram of Setup

Figure 2. Low and High Order Fringe Area - $1\frac{1}{2}$ and 4 Fringes, 150 LPI Grid, 63.5" Incidence Angle - .0033 inch Per Fringe Displacement After Impact.

Figure 3. Moire Fringes (3) About Lower Hole After Fatigue Cycling. Inspected with 500-LPI Grid: 25-Ply Gr/Ep Specimen.

Figure 4. Moire Fringes Around Cold-Worked Hole.